

ISic3207

I.Sicily inscription 3207

Language

Latin

Type

honorific; building

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]I,ALI[---]

2. [---][pla]teae AM[---]

3. [---]C,A[---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493969

EDR 139555

EDCS 22200388

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle

collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 42
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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 77 = Libertini
(1981) 124

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